

Blind nonlinear source separation using DCT modeling

Marc Ibanyez
TSC Dept.
UPC
Barcelona, Spain
marc.ibanyez@estudiantat.upc.edu

Ana I. Perez-Neira
SRCOM Unit
CTTC - CERCA, UPC
Castelldefels, Spain
ana.perez@cttc.es
ICREA Academia

Miguel A. Lagunas
TSC Dept.
UPC
Barcelona, Spain
miguel.angel.lagunas@upc.edu

Abstract—The challenge lies in the blind separation of sources from a non-linear mixture, specifically focusing on non-linear mutual coupling mixtures. In this study, the authors revisit the pioneering method introduced by C. Jutten and G. Herault (J-H) for source separation in linear mixtures and propose an architecture incorporating adaptive non-linearities. The mixing architecture assumes that each original source at the observations is affected by the addition of a non-linear function of the other independent source, exemplifying non-linear mutual coupling. Therefore, the paper is restricted to a non-linear structure assumed for non-linear mixtures. The objective is to demonstrate the expressivity of the trigonometric approach, based on the Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT), in modeling non-linear systems. The resulting separation network and algorithm mimic the original J-H method by identifying the non-linear blocks of the mix and separating the two independent sources with extremely low complexity.

Index Terms—Source separation, nonlinear mutual coupling, Discrete Cosinus Transform.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the pioneering work of J. Herault and C. Jutten [1] (referred to in this work as the J-H method or algorithm), the problem of non-linear source separation has received significant attention in the literature. Much of the research has focused on addressing the ill-posed problem of recovering original independent sources from a non-linear mixture. From this extensive body of work, two basic approaches have emerged.

The first approach involves using multiple layers, based on the idea that inverting a non-linear mixture requires multilayer structures. For instance, reference [6] presents a two-layer structure, where the first layer approximates the non-linearity followed by an output layer. This method transforms the time-invariant non-linear mix into a locally linear problem, albeit with much greater complexity than the original work [1]. The advantage of this approach is that it does not require any model for the mixing process. Techniques such as splines and wavelet transforms (see [11] for single-source ICA-Independent Component Analysis) fall under this category.

This work was supported by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 through the project IRENE (PID2020-115323RB-C31) and also by the Catalan government through the project SGR-Cat 2021-01207.

The second approach assumes a specific structure for the non-linear mix, namely post non-linear mixtures. Reference [7] is an example of this approach, where the mix is assumed to be a linear block followed by non-linear sensors. The separation network architecture involves non-linear processing of the sensed signals followed by a linear separation network. This method also increases complexity compared to [1] and is restricted to specific mixing structures. In addition to references [6] and [7], there are several excellent works and reviews on the topic, including references [8], [9], and [10]. This paper follows this second approach (i.e., restricted structure of the mix), specifically dealing with mutual coupling between array transmitter antennas in the field of antenna array processing.

The J-H algorithm was originally designed to separate M independent sources from N linear mixtures. It modifies the learning rule for uncorrelated sources by including higher-order (non-linear) functions necessary for independence, but not sufficient. The uncorrelation of the sources is achieved by minimizing the resulting powers of the signals at the output of the separation network. This document focuses on the case of two sensors and two independent sources.

The aim of this paper is to extend the original network and algorithm of [1] to handle mutual coupling, where each source receives the addition of an instantaneous non-linear coupling from the other sources. To achieve this extension, it is necessary to revisit the signal processing fundamentals of the J-H method. The J-H algorithm effectively handles non-linear mixtures by approximating the non-linear components with a linear mixture that optimally fits the actual non-linearity of the mixture.

Section II revisits the J-H algorithm, focusing on aspects that lack a straightforward extension to non-linear mixtures. Adjustments are required for the concept of power attributes of the sources to address the independence issue. The separation algorithms need to transition from the original direct and instantaneous approach in the J-H work to an iterative process.

After addressing the conflicts of the original algorithm, Section III adapts the formalism to suit the requirements for separating sources in the non-linear mutual coupling mixture.

As the separation network necessitates the incorporation of nonlinear blocks, its architecture requires adaptive nonlinear

functions suitable for learning. The authors, as reported in [2], employ an adaptive single input-single output non-linear approximation based on a DCT (Discrete Cosine Transform) with a low number of coefficients (maximum 6) that capture 99% of the energy of the original instantaneous non-linear system. The learning rule uses a basic gradient (Least Mean Squares or LMS-like) approach with full control over misadjustment and learning rate trade-off. This approximation has been successfully used in on-the-air computing [3] and in developing a two-layer neural network for complex classification and regression problems (the so-called ENN - Expressive Neural Network) [4]. Section IV integrates the DCT approximation into the architecture of the proposed separation network, demonstrating that the expressivity of the DCT significantly enhances performance compared to the original network [1].

Section V describes various scenarios and the performance of the proposed separation network, highlighting differences from the original J-H separation algorithm. Section VI presents the conclusions.

II. THE J-H ALGORITHM

Basically, the two inputs $x_1(n)$ and $x_2(n)$ are a linear mixture of two sources as shown in Fig.1. The left part of the figure represents the linear mixture of the two independent sources $z_1(n)$ and $z_2(n)$ with the coefficients of the mix a_{12} and a_{21} respectively. This is the linear mutual coupling problem. Note that the mix network is a feed-forward processing. The separation network, in cascade with the mix network is a feed-back processing. In [1] it is remarked that $|a_{12}a_{21}| < 1$ for stability and/or to preserve the order of the resulting separated outputs.

Fig. 1. From left to right. Instantaneous mix network of two independent sources with processing matrix $\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & 1 \end{bmatrix}$. Next, the separation network associated to a processing matrix \mathbf{W} .

The linear mix is defined by (1)

$$\begin{aligned} x_1(n) &= z_1(n) + a_{12}z_2(n) \\ x_2(n) &= z_2(n) + a_{21}z_1(n) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Concerning the separation network, the formulation is (2), where it is assumed that during learning the weights are not the actual ones from the mix, namely c_{12} and c_{21} and the corresponding outputs are $y_1(n)$ and $y_2(n)$ respectively:

$$\begin{pmatrix} y_1(n) \\ y_2(n) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} x_1(n) \\ x_2(n) \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} 0 & c_{12} \\ c_{21} & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} y_1(n) \\ y_2(n) \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

This equation can be solved iteratively starting with two values for the outputs and successive iterations in (2). The authors in J-H avoid the use of iterations since the linear mixtures (2) can be solved as indicated in (3).

$$\begin{pmatrix} y_1(n) \\ y_2(n) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & c_{12} \\ c_{21} & 1 \end{pmatrix}^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} x_1(n) \\ x_2(n) \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The equation on the right of (3), provides a simple and fast manner to compute the outputs from the input in the feed-back network.

Unfortunately, the procedure indicated in (3) cannot be used for the case of nonlinear mixtures. For accurate identification during separation, nonlinear mixtures necessitate the use of iterative methods.

Afterward, Jutten and Herault implement a learning rule to decorrelate the outputs by minimizing the powers of $y_1(n)$ and $y_2(n)$, resulting in a symmetric learning process proportional to the product $y_1(n)y_2(n)$. To break this symmetry, they heuristically propose the use of odd non-linear functions, specifically $sh(y_1(n))$ multiplied by $y_2(n)^3$. Interestingly, the rule for uncorrelated sources is derived from the gradient of the instantaneous power of $y_1(n)$ using equation (2), although equation (3) is implemented. It's worth noting, for instance, that the relationship between the power of $y_1(n)$ and c_{12} is more intricate in (3) than in (2).

Despite these considerations and the heuristic transition from uncorrelated to independent sources, the performance of the J-H algorithm remains excellent.

A more formal approach involves questioning the significance of signal power. Power/energy are concepts rooted in electrical circuits, emerging with the square of the magnitude of voltages and currents in and electrical circuit. The inquiry arises: to what extent does of the signal contribute to its relevance in source separation or new problems to come? Perhaps relevance should be assessed as a positive measure, with varying emphasis depending on magnitude. In other words, by selecting the relevance of $y_1(n)$ as $Ry_1(n)$ in (4), the gradient of $Ry_1(n)$ with respect to c_{12} becomes (5). Similar considerations apply to inhibition, leading to the replacement of relevance $REy_1(n)$ in (4) to obtain the conventional setup of the J-H algorithm in (6).

$$Ry_1(n) = sh\left(\frac{y_1(n)}{2}\right)^2; REy_1(n) = sh\left(\frac{y_1(n)}{2}\right)^2 y_2(n)^2 \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{c_{12}} Ry_1(n) &= sh(y_1(n)) \nabla_{c_{12}} y_1(n) = \\ &= sh(y_1(n)) y_2(n) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{c_{12}} REy_1(n) &= sh(y_1(n)) y_2(n)^2 \nabla_{c_{12}} y_1(n) = \\ &= sh(y_1(n)) y_2(n)^3. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

For the separating network proposed in this paper, the power 4 of the data, i.e. $Ry_1(n) = y_1(n)^4$, has been used as relevance measure. The gradient rules derived from this relevance will be listed hereafter in Section IV.

The preceding paragraphs argue that using relevance functions other than squares may better suit statistical purposes. In summary, sequences are not limited to electrical voltages or currents; they are raw data for which power or energy (squared power) may not be the best metric to reflect their relevance for new processing goals. As demonstrated in this paper, using the fourth power of the data along with the trigonometric approximation provided by the DCT is sufficient for the scenarios tested in Section V. The separation structure effectively isolates the original sources, while the non-linearities in the separation network accurately identify the original non-linearities in the mutual coupling mix.

III. ADAPTIVE NON-LINEARITY

As specifically described in [2] and applied in various contexts in [3] and [4], a particular non-linearity can be effectively approximated using the Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) within the range of $[-1,1]$. Utilizing the DCT proves advantageous in terms of the minimal number of coefficients needed for a satisfactory approximation of any function within this interval. This trigonometric approximation method has been employed by other authors to solve systems of differential equations, as for instance in [5].

For any $f(x)$ such that $f(-1) = 1$ and $f(1) = 1$ the DCT approximation is given by (7), where N is the scanning precision of x , usually set to $N = 512$, x_u is a normalization needed to map the input x to $1, 2, \dots, N$, assuming the input is confined to $[1, 1]$.

$$f(x) = \sum_{q=1}^Q c(q) \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2N}(i(q) - 1)(2x_u - 1)\right) \quad (7)$$

$$N = 512; \quad i = \{2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12\}; \quad x_u = N \frac{x + 1}{2}.$$

Since most of the non-linearities encountered in practice are odd-functions, i.e. $f(-x) = -f(x)$, like compressors, expanders, etc, the index q in (7) reduces to even integers. Furthermore, for these frequent non-linearities using only $Q = 6$ provides excellent approximations of $f(x)$, which retain above 99% of the energy of the original function.

The coefficients are updated with the snapshots of cosines included in (7). This snapshot has constant power given by half the number of cosines, i.e. there are Q cosines then the power is $Q/2$. The cosines are uncorrelated, so the trade-off rate of convergence and miss-adjustment are controlled with the step equal to $6\alpha/Q$, where α is the miss-adjustment (100 α %) and the convergence rate is close to $\log_e 10/2\alpha$. See [2] for more details.

IV. NONLINEAR MIXTURE SOURCE SEPARATION

The non-linear mixing network for the non-linear mutual coupling is shown in Fig.2, where $f(\cdot)$ and $g(\cdot)$ are instantaneous nonlinear systems. The independent sources are $z_1(n)$ and $z_2(n)$ and the mix outputs are $x_1(n)$ and $x_2(n)$ respectively. The formulation of the mix of the sources $z_1(n)$

and $z_2(n)$, where both $f(\cdot)$ and $g(\cdot)$ are continuous functions with continuous derivatives in $[-1, 1]$, is shown in (8).

$$\begin{aligned} x_1(n) &= z_1(n) + a_{12}f(z_2(n)) \\ x_2(n) &= z_2(n) + a_{21}g(z_1(n)) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Fig. 2. The non-linear mutual coupling mix. Architecture of the instantaneous mix of sources $z_1(n)$ and $z_2(n)$. The formulation of the mix is shown in (8)

Concerning stability, note that for a given value of the source $z_2(n)$, the gain in the branch connecting this input with the adder is $a_{12}\nabla_{x=z_2}f$. This suggests that the gain is regulated by the maximum of the derivative of the nonlinear response with respect to the input. In essence, the adjustment of the mixture coefficients must be more conservative compared to the case of linear mixtures to ensure the network operates within the stability region.

The separation network is shown in Fig.3, where $F(\cdot)$ and $G(\cdot)$ are the DCT models of the non-linearities in the separation network. This structure separates the sources whenever the mix functions $f(\cdot)$ and $g(\cdot)$ are continuous with bounded derivatives in the range $[-1, 1]$.

Fig. 3. The separation network for nonlinear mixtures.

The formulation of the separation network is (9). The non-linearities are modeled by a DCT with six coefficients. Indices $i(q)$ equal to $\{2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12\}$, $N = 512$. In (9) it can be seen the DCT model of the non-linear system. It is important to mention that the size of $Q = 6$ is more than necessary for most cases.

$$\begin{aligned}
y_1(n) &= x_1(n) - c_{120}F(y_2(n)) = x_1(n) - c_{120}y_{21}(n) \\
y_2(n) &= x_2(n) - c_{210}G(y_1(n)) = x_2(n) - c_{210}y_{12}(n) \\
y_{21}(n) &= F(y_2(n)) = \\
&= \sum_{q=1}^6 c_f(q) \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2N}(i(q)-1)(y_2(n)+1)N-1\right)
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

The two first equations in (9) are solved iteratively (the number of iterations use to be within the range 5 to 10). The objective is the minimization of the relevance of y_1 , defined as the power 4 of y_1 (i.e., $Ry_1(n) = y_1^4(n)$). The gradients and rules for altering the various coefficients are depicted in (10). In the simulations, a step size of $\mu_2 = 0.01 * 2/Q$ and $\mu_1 = 0.01$ were employed.

$$\begin{aligned}
\nabla_{c_{120}}y_1^3 &= -(y_1(n)^2)y_{21}(n) \\
\nabla_{c_{110}}y_2^3 &= -(y_2(n)^2)y_{12}(n) \\
\nabla_{c_f}y_1^4 &= -(y_1(n)^2)c_{120}\nabla_{c_f}y_{21} = -(y_1(n)^3)c_{120}\mathbf{x}_f(n) \\
\nabla_{c_g}y_2^4 &= -(y_2(n)^3)c_{210}\nabla_{c_g}y_{12} = -(y_2(n)^3)c_{210}\mathbf{x}_g(n) \\
\mathbf{x}_f(n) &= \left(\dots\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2N}(i(q)-1)(y_2(n)+1)N-1\right)\right) \\
\mathbf{x}_g(n) &= \left(\dots\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2N}(i(q)-1)(y_1(n)+1)N-1\right)\right) \\
c_{120} &= c_{120} + \mu_1 y_{21}(n) y_1^3(n) \\
c_{210} &= c_{210} + \mu_1 y_{12}(n) y_2^3(n) \\
\mathbf{c}_f &= \mathbf{c}_f + \mu_2 c_{120} y_1^3(n) \mathbf{x}_f(n) \\
\mathbf{c}_g &= \mathbf{c}_g + \mu_2 c_{210} y_2^3(n) \mathbf{x}_g(n) \\
\mathbf{c}_f &= -\frac{\mathbf{c}_f}{\text{sum}(\mathbf{c}_f)} \\
\mathbf{c}_g &= -\frac{\mathbf{c}_g}{\text{sum}(\mathbf{c}_g)}
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

Please note that the two last equations in (10) normalize the updated coefficients of the DCT model to ensure that the values of the functions $F(\cdot)$ and $G(\cdot)$ fall within the range of -1 and 1 at the borders of the interval $[-1, 1]$.

V. SIMULATIONS

The simulations employed 3 scenarios:

- 1) A linear mixture of two uniform distributions, spectrally white.
- 2) A non-linear mixture of an input with 2 sinusoids with another input with 3 sinusoids. All 5 sinusoids have different carriers.
- 3) A non-linear mixture of a sinusoid with uniform distributed white noise.

In all cases, the learning starts after 10^5 samples, the size of the epoch is 4×10^5 , the mixing coefficients are $[1 \ 0.5; 0.3 \ 1]$. In the non-linear mixtures, $f(\cdot)$ is a compander and $g(\cdot)$ is an expander, both are logarithmic.

A. Scenario 1

The figures from Fig.4 to Fig.9 refer to the scenario of two signals that are uniformly distributed. The first three plots (i.e., from Fig.4 to Fig.6) show the performance of the J-H algorithm; then, the last three (i.e., from Fig.7 to Fig.9) show the performance of the proposed DCT network.

Fig. 4. Performance in separating the linear mixture of two signals uniformly distributed. J-H technique. Identification of the mix. Red: initial, green: actual, blue: estimated.

Fig. 5. Performance in separating the linear mixture of two signals uniformly distributed. J-H technique. Histograms of the two outputs.

Fig. 6. Performance in separating the linear mixture of two signals uniformly distributed. J-H technique. Gradient evolution and linear coefficients estimated.

NLC from 2 to 1: Initial (r) Final (b)

Fig. 7. Performance in separating the linear mixture of two signals uniformly distributed. The proposed technique. Identification of the mix. Red: initial, green: actual, blue: estimated.

NLC from 2 to 1: Initial (r) Final (b)

Fig. 10. Performance of the J-H algorithm. Adjustment of the estimated non-linearities. Red: initial, green: actual, blue: estimated.

Fig. 8. Performance in separating the linear mixture of two signals uniformly distributed. The proposed technique. Histograms of the two outputs.

Fig. 11. Performance of the J-H algorithm. Periodogram of first output.

B. Scenario 2

The second example is separating the a nonlinear mix (logarithmic compander/expander) of a signal with two carriers with another signal with three carriers. The performance of the J-H can be seen in figures from Fig.10 to Fig.13. Whereas the performance of the proposed technique is shown in figures from Fig.14 to Fig.17.

Observing figures from Fig.10 to Fig.17, it becomes apparent that while the J-H algorithm succeeds in separating the

Fig. 12. Performance of the J-H algorithm. Periodogram of the second output.

Fig. 9. Performance in separating the linear mixture of two signals uniformly distributed. The proposed technique. Gradient evolution and linear coefficients estimated.

Fig. 13. Performance of the J-H algorithm. Evolution of the gradient and estimated coefficients.

Fig. 14. Performance of the proposed technique. Adjustment of the estimated non-linearities. Red: initial, green: actual, blue: estimated.

Fig. 15. Performance of the proposed technique. Periodogram of first output.

Fig. 16. Performance of the proposed technique. Periodogram of the second output.

Fig. 17. Performance of the proposed technique. Evolution of the gradient and estimated coefficients.

sources in this scenario, it essentially offers the optimal linear approximation to the non-linearity. However, its convergence rate decreases, and it struggles to identify the coefficients accurately. Additionally, in other scenarios, it fails in achieving a satisfactory separation of the sources. In contrast, the proposed algorithm demonstrates an adequate convergence rate, accurately estimates the non-linearity influencing the mix, and appropriately adjusts the coefficients. As expected, these coefficients reflect the impact of the derivatives of the non-linearities, with a greater coefficient for the compander and a lower coefficient for the expander.

C. Scenario 3

The following figures (from Fig.18 to Fig.25) demonstrate the performance of the proposed DCT-based separation scheme for scenario 3, which consists in the denoising of a single carrier. These figures illustrate the method's ability to identify the non-linearities involved in mutual coupling, which is something that cannot be done by the J-H method. The coupling non-linearities are well estimated, as shown by Fig. 18 and Fig. 19, and by the histograms of the separated sources in Fig. 20 and Fig. 21, which display the carrier and the uniformly distributed noise. The mixed input in Fig. 22 and reveals the noisy carrier, while the separated sinusoidal source in Fig. Fig. 23 successfully recovers its constant envelope, with its periodogram in Fig.24 showing only minor harmonic distortion at -23 dB. Additionally, the separated noise source in Fig.25 is spectrally flat, as expected for a white uniformly distributed source.

Fig. 18. Coupling function f compander, initial actual and estimated. Red: initial, green: actual, blue: estimated.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

As with other scenarios involving non-linear processing, the DCT model demonstrates significantly greater expressivity than other models, including other trigonometric ones. This has proven true for problems in regression, classification, and the viability of systems for over-the-air computing. In this paper, the basic source separation model developed by Jutten and Herault is enhanced not only to separate non-linear mixtures resulting from non-linear coupling but also to identify the non-linearities involved in the mutual coupling.

LC from 1 to 2: Initial (r) Final (b) Actual

Fig. 19. Coupling function g expander, initial actual and estimated. Red: initial, green: actual, blue: estimated.

Fig. 20. Histogram of the separated sinusoidal source.

Additionally, stability control for learning these non-linearities is easily integrated into the algorithm.

However, the proposed method does face two complexity-related challenges. First, the number of coefficients to update during the learning phase increases from two in the traditional algorithm to a maximum of fourteen (up to six coefficients per DCT model used). Second, the network output must be computed iteratively since the shortcut used in the linear case is not applicable to the non-linear case. Despite this added complexity compared to the original J-H algorithm, the

Fig. 21. Histogram of the separated uniformly distributed source.

Fig. 22. Input 1 to the separation network (i.e., mixture).

Fig. 23. Separated sinusoidal source.

Fig. 24. Periodogram of the separated sinusoidal source.

Fig. 25. Periodogram of the separated white noise source.

proposed method remains significantly less complex than other alternatives in non-linear blind source separation. Moreover, accurately identifying the shape of the non-linearity provides valuable diagnostics for correcting non-linear coupling, as in the cases of radiating or receiving arrays.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Jutten, J. Herault. "Blind separation of sources, PartI: An adaptive algorithm based on neuromimetic architecture". EURASIP. Signal Processing 24 (1991) pp. 1-10.
- [2] A. Perez-Neira, M. Martinez and M. Lagunas, "Adaptive Function Approximation Based on the Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT)," in 2023 27th International Conference on Circuits, Systems, Communications and Computers (CSCC), Rhodes (Rodos) Island, Greece, 2023 pp. 224-231.
- [3] M.M. Gost, A. I. Perez, M.A. Lagunas. " DCT-Based Air Interface Design for Function Computation". IEEE Open Journal of Signal Processing, Vol 4,pp. 44-51, DOI 10.1109/OJSP.2023.324.1584. Feb. 2023.
- [4] M.M. Gost, Ana I. Perez, M.A. Lagunas. " ENN: A Neural Network with DCT Adaptive Activation Functions". IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing. Pages 1-10, DOI 10.1109/JSSTSP.2024.3361154. Feb 2024.
- [5] S. Lee, H. -Y. Kwak and J. -S. No, "Effect of the Period of the Fourier Series Approximation for Binarized Neural Network," 2022 International Conference on Artificial Intelligence in Information and Communication (ICAIIIC), Jeju Island, Korea, Republic of, 2022, pp. 262-265.
- [6] L. Wang, T. Ohtsuki. "Nonlinear Blind Source Separation Unifying Vanishing Component Analysis and Temporal Structure". IEEE Access, Vol.6, pp. 42837-42850, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2860683, July 30, 2018.
- [7] S. Achard, C. Jutten. "Identifiability of post nonlinear mixtures". IEEE Signal Processing Letters, Vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 423-426, doi: 10.1109/LSP.2005.845593.
- [8] L.B. Almeida. "Nonlinear Source Separation". Springer Cham. Pp 31-77 (Chapter 3). Series: Synthesis Lectures on Signal Processing. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-02526-6>.
- [9] C. Jutten, J. Karhunen. "Advances in Nonlinear Blind Source Separation" ICA 2003, April 2003, Proceedings of the Conference. pp. 245-256. Nara, Japan.
- [10] Bahram Ensandoust, Massoud Babaie Zedeh, Bertrand Rivet, Christian Jutten. "Blind Source Separation in Nonlinear Mixtures". IEEE Trans. On Signal Processing, 2017, 65(16), pp. 4339-4352. 10.1109/TSP.2017.2708025 hal-01552273.
- [11] M. Kemiha, A. Kacha. "Single-Channel Blind Separation Using Adaptive Mode Separation- Based Wavelet Transform and ICA Single-Channel Separation". WSEAS Transactions on Signal Processing, vol. 18, pp. 77-88, 2022. Doi:10.3739/232014.2022.18.11